

EXAMINING THE RELATION BETWEEN SPIRITUALITY, WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY AND ORGANIZATION CULTURE, PERFORMANCE – A PATHWAY TO ORGANIZATION EXCELLENCE

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ABSTRACT

Employees at clear-purpose organizations feel inspired, committed, and part of a larger purpose, which fosters a sense of belonging. According to a study that was published in the MIT Sloan Management Review, related to "**Toxic Culture Driving Employee Turnover**" reveals that a toxic corporate culture is 10 times more significant than compensation in predicting employee turnover. This indicates that strong interventions must be put in place at work to enhance organizational culture. Studies show that a spiritually enriched workplace culture encourages a sense of belonging, respect, and trust among employees, resulting in a more peaceful and positive work environment. Therefore, the researchers have examined how workplace spirituality affects organizational culture in this study. The responses of 105 participants who were given two structured questionnaires—one with workplace spirituality (WPS) and organization culture (OCTAPACE) parameters and other an opinion survey is analysed in this descriptive qualitative and quantitative study. WPS and organizational culture were found to be strongly positively correlated by Spearman Rank Correlation. To support their hypothesis, the researchers have proposed a theoretical model that highlights the relationship between Workplace Spirituality (WPS) = OCTAPACE (Positive Organization Culture), which leads to the fourth P, Purpose of Quadruple Bottom Line) = Organization Performance = Organization Excellence.

Keywords: Workplace Spirituality, Organization Culture (OCTAPACE), Organization Performance and Organization Excellence

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance, engagement, and long-term economic success all depend on one of the major factors like a strong corporate culture and a purpose-driven strategy. **Udai Pareek and T.V. Rao** proposed the OCTAPACE culture for organization success as below:

1. Openness: Promoting unrestricted, honest dialogue and idea exchange.
2. Confrontation: Dealing with concerns and difficulties head-on in a positive manner.
3. Trust: Encouraging mutual trust and faith in one another's motives and deeds.
4. Authenticity: Promoting sincere and truthful conduct in which individuals stay loyal to their principles and identities.
5. Proaction: Being proactive and foreseeing issues before they happen as opposed to responding to them after they happen.

6. **Autonomy:** Providing workers with independence and authority over their work so they may take initiative and make choices.
7. **Collaboration:** Encouraging collaboration and teamwork so that individuals can work together to achieve shared objectives.
8. **Experimentation:** Promoting creativity and the investigation of novel concepts and methods.

One exceptional contribution for enhancing the organization culture, performance and building purpose oriented organizations, has also been made by **Ayman Sawaf (2014)**, who introduced the 4th bottom line to the business world that is the 4th P, Purpose which includes concepts like "spirituality," "ethics," "purpose," "culture," and "compassion," provides inspiration for a business and goes beyond humanistic values. The concepts of the 4th **bottom line** that elevate the business operations as spiritual form, **Spirituality**, that entails feeling of being connected to others and the natural world, motivating actions for collective betterment rather than individual salvation," **Bailey, J (2024)**, highlights the importance of workplace spirituality that can develop amongst the employees the feeling of togetherness leading to positive organization climate, culture and organization excellence.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Workplace Spirituality, Organization Culture, Organization Performance, Sustainability: A comprehensive analysis of workplace spirituality literature from 2000 to December 2022 is presented by **Dubey, S., & Gupta, O. (2023)**, emphasizing the development of the idea and its impact on organizational culture and performance. **Vallabh, P., & Vallabh, G. (2016)** investigated how workplace spirituality mediated the relationship between effectiveness and organizational culture. **Stead, J. G., & Stead, W. E. (2013)** talked about how incorporating spirituality into business procedures might result in competitive advantages based on sustainability. **F. Karakas (2010)** investigated how workplace spirituality improves worker performance and organizational effectiveness. According to Karakas, there are three main advantages of workplace spirituality: enhancing workers' quality of life and well-being; giving them a sense of direction and significance at work; and encouraging a sense of community and interconnectedness among coworkers. When taken as a whole, these elements enhance organizational performance. A paradigm for evaluating how workplace spirituality affects organizational performance through values alignment was proposed by **Jurkiewicz, C. L., & Giacalone, R. A. (2004)**.

Research Problem Statement

Workplace Spirituality has a positive impact on Organization Culture.

Objectives of the Study:

- 1) To explore the relationship between Workplace Spirituality, Organization Culture, Organization Performance and Organization Excellence.
- 2) Propose a theoretical model that demonstrates relationship between workplace spirituality, organization culture, organization excellence and organization performance.

Theoretical Framework:

1) Theory: The foundation of this study is the Spiritual Leadership theory, which contends that spiritual virtues like selfless love, faith, and hope foster a positive workplace culture.

Businesses that adopt spiritual leadership improve the ethical work culture, job happiness, and well-being of their employees.

2) VARIABLES OF THE STUDY AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP:

a) Variables of the study:

- **Workplace Spirituality: Workplace Spirituality**, "the recognition that employees have an inner life that nourishes and is nourished by meaningful work that takes place in the context of community," **Ashmos and Duchon (2000)**
- **Organization Culture**: "A pattern of shared basic assumptions that the group learned as it solved its problems of external adaptation and internal integration, that has worked well enough to be considered valid and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems." **Edgar H. Schein (1985)**.
- **Organizational Excellence**: The triple bottom line – Profit, People, Planet (Sustainability framework) by John Elkington (1994) and the 4th P, purpose as proposed by **Ayman Sawaf (2014)** together form framework for organization excellence models which are mentioned and measured in different ways by business excellence awards of various countries, e.g EFQM excellence awards, Global excellence awards, Asian excellence awards.

b) Relationship among variables: The independent variable workplace spirituality impacts the dependant variable organization culture.

H1: Workplace Spirituality has a positive impact on Organization Culture.

Research Methodology:

- 1) **Research Design:** The study is descriptive qualitative and quantitative in nature. The researcher carried out literature review on workplace spirituality, organization culture, organization performance and excellence followed by 2 online surveys, analysis and model conceptualization.
- 2) **Sampling Design:** 105 respondents from Mumbai both working and non-working were administered survey using Non – Probability convenience sampling method.
- 3) **Data Design:** Primary data was collected through online survey that was conducted using 2 structured questionnaires, one of which one was the opinion survey, other questionnaire measuring WPS and Organization Culture (based on OCTAPACE framework) constructs with Cronbach alpha of 0.92 and 0.96 for each of the constructs respectively. Spearman Rank Correlation and Pie charts were used to analyse the scores of workplace spirituality and organization culture and findings were reported.

Data Analysis – Part I – Opinion Survey on Workplace Spirituality and Organization Culture (62 respondents)

Q) Diagram 1, shows responses to Opinion of People on Spirituality at Workplace, Impact of WPS on Organization Culture and Organization Performance (Ref: Q1,3,4 of questionnaire)

Diagram 1

Interpretation: It can be observed that 79.3% respondents (both strongly agree and agree) to promoting spiritual practices/ spirituality at workplace, 11.29% neutral opinion and 9.68% (both strongly disagree and disagree) disagreed. Furthermore, 77.42% respondents (both strongly agree and agree) and 79.03% respondents (both strongly agree and agree) that workplace spirituality can help in achieving overall positive organization culture and improving overall organization performance respectively whereas 14.52 % responses in each of the case have neutral opinion while a minority round about 6 to 8 % have strongly disagreed and disagreed.

Q2) Do you think promoting spirituality or spiritual practices at workplace can help in improving organization culture in the below areas. Tick as many.

Diagram 2

Interpretation: It can be observed that respondents believe that workplace spirituality can be helpful in promoting all values of OCTAPACE culture, of which the top 3 highest rated values which people believe can be inculcated through spirituality are: openness 75.8% and trust 61.3 % and collaboration, 59.7%

Data Analysis – Part II – Workplace Spirituality and Organization Culture Questionnaire (43 Respondents)

Q1) I, believe it is important for the organizations to have purpose and meaning (focus more on making a positive impact on society, the environment, or their stakeholders, overall upliftment of humanity) in addition to only profit goal.

Diagram 3

Interpretation: 83.72% respondents (both agree and strongly agree) that organizations should be purpose oriented and be more meaningful, 2.33% are neutral while 13.95% strongly disagree and disagree.

Q2&3) Correlation Analysis of Workplace Spirituality and Organization Culture Scores of 43 respondents

Diagram 4: Scatter plot showing correlation between Workplace Spirituality Scores and Organization Culture Scores

Interpretation: The Value of spearman rho correlation $r_s = 0.6659$. Technically it is a positive correlation between Workplace Spirituality and Organization Culture Scores and a

strong one (Refer Spearman Rank Correlation Interpretation Table, Adapted from Dancey and Reidy, 2004)

Q4) WPS impact on Organization Culture, Organization Performance and Organization Excellence.

Diagram 5

Interpretation: It can be observed that 59.52% respondents (both strongly agree and agree) and 54.76% respondents (both strongly agree and agree), 52.38% respondents (both strongly agree and agree), that workplace spirituality can help in achieving overall positive organization culture and improving overall organization performance and organization excellence respectively, whereas 30-38% responses in each of the case have neutral opinion while a round about 9 to 12 % have strongly disagreed and disagreed.

FINDINGS

Following are the findings of the study:

- 1) The average of responses to question no 1, 3, 4, of opinion survey show 78.49 % respondents and average of Q4 of WPS and Organization Culture instrument reveals 55.56% of respondents agree that spirituality/ spiritual interventions/ WPS at workplace should be encouraged and that it can help in improving overall organization culture (OCTAPACE – positive), organization performance and organization excellence.
- 2) The correlation strength of WPS and Organization Culture reveals strong correlation, $r_s = 0.6659$, highlighting that independent variable workplace spirituality has a positive impact on organization culture.

Limitations and Scope of the Study: The model is limited to a prima facie theoretical model and is for pilot study, needs to be tested further on a large scale by observing in long run. Further comparative research can be conducted on companies’ organization culture with and without workplace spirituality interventions.

Conclusion with Proposed Model: The data analysis and findings of the current study from primary data of questionnaire have demonstrated workplace spirituality can lead to positive organization culture and purpose leading to acceptance of alternate hypothesis. As it has been

observed from the literature that a positive organization culture, or OCTAPACE elements are crucial for success of organization performance. The 4th P, Purpose of quadruple bottom line is also one of the important factors of organization excellence. Hence the model is as below:

Fig 1. Proposed Model by the Researchers of Current Study

REFERENCES

1. Kothari.C.R, Garg.G, (2014), Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques, 3rd Edition. ISBN:978-81-224-3623-5
2. <https://johnelkington.com/archive/TBL-elkington-chapter.pdf>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fourth_bottom_line
4. Sull, D., Sull, C., & Zweig, B. (2022, January 11). *Toxic culture is driving the great resignation*. MIT Sloan Management Review.
5. Ashmos, D. P., & Duchon, D. (2000). Spirituality at work: A conceptualization and measure. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 9(2), 134-145.
6. Bailey, J. (2024, October 7). *Spirituality is the shy hope in my heart that I can co-create a better world*. The Guardian. Retrieved from
7. Dubey, S., & Gupta, O. (2023). Workplace spirituality: A systematic review and future research agenda. *Journal of Business Ethics*. Advance online publication.
8. Vallabh, P., & Vallabh, G. (2016). Role of workplace spirituality in relationship between organizational culture and effectiveness. *Management and Labour Studies*, 41(3), 1–16.Sage Journals
9. Stead, J. G., & Stead, W. E. (2013). Building spiritual capabilities to sustain sustainability-based competitive advantages. *Journal of Management, Spirituality & Religion*, 10(2), 95–113.Wikipedia
10. Karakas, F. (2010). Spirituality and performance in organizations: A literature review. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 94(1), 89–106.Southeastern Oklahoma State University+2SpringerLink+2SSRN+2

11. Jurkiewicz, C. L., & Giacalone, R. A. (2004). A values framework for measuring the impact of workplace spirituality on organizational performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 49(2), 129–142. Academia
12. Schein, E. H. (1990). *Organizational culture*. *American Psychologist*, 45(2), 109-119.
13. Fry, L. W. (2003). Toward a theory of spiritual leadership. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 14(6), 693-727.